

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS AND PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS OF THE TlSe – CuCr₂Te₄ SYSTEM

Aliyev Imir,

Doctor of Chemistry, prof. hands. lab.

Ahmedova Naiba,

PhD an der Chimie,

*Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry named after M.F.Nagiyev
of the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Gashimov Khalig,

Ph.D., Associate Prof.,

Azerbaijan State Economic University

Aliyev Ibrahim,

Master,

Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry

Ahmedova Ceyran,

Ph.D., Associate Prof.,

*Adiyaman University, Faculty of Arts and
Sciences, Faculty of Chemistry, Turkey*

Abstract

Using DTA, XRF, MSA methods, as well as by measuring microhardness and determining density, composite materials in the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system were synthesized and a T-x phase diagram was constructed. It has been established that the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system is a quasi-binary section of the quasi-ternary TlSe-CuTe-Cr₂Te₃ system. Solid solutions based on TlSe at room temperature reach up to 3 mol % CuCr₂Te₄, and based on CuCr₂Te₄ solid solutions up to -12 mol % TlSe. The joint crystallization of TlSe and CuCr₂Te₄ compounds ends with a double eutectic of composition 20 mol % CuCr₂Te₄ and temperature 240°C.

Keywords: system, composite materials, eutectic, phase diagram, density

Introduction

Obtaining and studying the physical-chemical properties of multicomponent composite materials with valuable, practically important characteristics is one of the main tasks of modern science. Thallium chalcogenides, the resulting ternary compounds and solid solutions based on them are photosensitive semiconductor materials [1-5].

There is a lot of information in the literature about chemical interactions in ternary and quaternary systems based on thallium chalcogenides [6-11]. Spinel-type compounds CuCr₂X₄ (X-S,Se,Te), formed on the basis of copper and chromium chalcogenides, are ferromagnetic materials [12,13]. The creation of a technology for the production of composite materials with ferromagnetic properties would stimulate the development of radio electronics, semiconductor technology and quantum electronics. The TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system is being studied for the first time.

The purpose of this work is the synthesis and physicochemical study of composite materials of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system and the construction of a T-x phase diagram.

The TlSe compound melts congruently at 330°C and crystallizes in a tetragonal syngony with lattice parameters: $a = 8.02$; $c = 7.00$ Å, space gr. I4/μm. Density, $\rho = 8.20$ g/cm³ [14]. The CuCr₂Te₄ compound melts congruently at 1155°C and crystallizes in the cubic syngony, lattice parameter $a = 11.134$ Å [15].

Experimental part

The starting components TlSe and CuCr₂Te₄ were synthesized from elemental chromium of 99.998% purity; thallium - Tl-000, Se - 99.999% and tellurium grade A-1, the latter was subjected to seven-fold zone purification. The alloys of the system were prepared by fusing calculated amounts of stoichiometric TlSe and CuCr₂Te₄ in quartz ampoules evacuated to 0.133 Pa at a temperature of 500-1200°C. To homogenize the alloys, the systems were annealed at 250°C for 350 hours.

The study was carried out using differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as measuring microhardness by determining density.

DTA of the system alloys was carried out on a TERMOSCAN-2 device at a speed of 5 deg/min. XRF was carried out on an X-ray device model D2 PHASER with CuK α radiation and a Ni filter. MSA of the alloys of the system was studied using a MIM-8 microscope on pre-etched sections polished with GOI paste. The microhardness of the system alloys was measured using a PMT-3 microhardness tester. The density of the alloys of the system was determined by the pycnometric method; toluene was used as a filler.

Results and discussion

Alloys of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system are found in the form of a molten mass in the temperature range of 500-1200°C and change color from bright gray to black. The relationship of alloys to the effects of the external environment was studied and it was found that

they are resistant to atmospheric oxygen, water and organic solvents. The alloys dissolve well in strong mineral acids (HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄). During the differential thermal analysis of the alloys, it was established that two and three endothermic effects were obtained in the thermograms of the samples. There are isothermal effects at 600°C, corresponding to the phase transition of

the CuCr₂Te₄ compound, and isothermal effects at 240°C, corresponding to the eutectic temperature. When studying the microstructure of alloys of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system, it was found that single-phase alloys are present around the main components. The microstructures of alloys containing 3, 15, 60 and 88 mol % of the CuCr₂Te₄ system are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Microstructures of alloys of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system.
1-3 mol %, 2-15 mol %, 3-60 mol %, 4-88 mol % CuCr₂Te₄.

As can be seen from Figure 1, single-phase CuCr₂Te₄ alloys with a concentration of 3 and 88 mol % - solid solution alloys based on TlSe and CuCr₂Te₄ compounds, respectively. Alloy 15 mol % CuCr₂Te₄ corresponds to the eutectic composition. A sample containing 60 mol % CuCr₂Te₄ is a two-phase alloy. These results indicate that the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system is quasi-binary.

The results of differential-thermal and microstructural analyzes were also confirmed by X-ray phase analysis. For this purpose, X-ray phase analysis of 3 mol %, 60 mol% and 88 mol % CuCr₂Te₄ alloys of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system of the same composition was carried out (Fig. 2).

Fig. 3. Diffraction patterns of alloys of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄.
1-TlSe, 2-3, 3-60, 4-88, 5-100 mol % CuCr₂Te₄.

Based on physicochemical analysis data, a phase diagram of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system was constructed (Fig. 3). It has been established that it is a quasi-binary section of the quasi-ternary system TlSe-CuTe-Cr₂Te₄ and belongs to the eutectic type. The liquidus of the system consists of monovariant curves of primary crystallization of δ -solid solutions based on TlSe, α and β -solid solutions based on CuCr₂Te₄. The joint crystallization of the δ and β phases ends at the double eutectic

point: $\mathcal{K} \leftrightarrow \delta + \beta$. The composition of the eutectic corresponds to 15 mol % CuCr₂Te₄ and melts at 240°C. The solubility at room temperature on the TlSe side is 3 mol % CuCr₂Te₄, and on the CuCr₂Te₄ side – 12 mol % TlSe, and at eutectic temperatures 10 and 17 mol %, respectively. The phase transition temperature of the CuCr₂Te₄ compound is 810°C. The temperature of the eutectic formed during the phase transition is 600°C.

Fig.3. Phase diagram of the TlSe – CuCr₂Te₄ system

Table 1.

Compositions, results DTA, measurements of density and microhardness of alloys of the TlSe – CuCr₂Te₄ system

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, q/sm ³	Microhardness, MPa	
TlSe	CuCr ₂ Te ₄			δ	α
				P=0,10 N	P=0,15 N
100	0,0	330	8,20	700	–
97	3,0	280,325	8,23	760	–
95	5,0	270,320	8,25	780	–
93	7,0	260,300	8,15	780	–
90	10	240,270	8,05	780	–
85	15	240	7,95	Eutek.	Eutek.
80	20	240,420	7,86	–	–
75	25	240,620	7,78	–	–
70	30	240,600,720	7,69	–	1880
60	40	240, 600,850	7,52	–	1880
50	50	240, 600,920	7,35	–	1880
40	60	240, 600,980	7,28	–	1880
30	70	240, 600,1025	7,02	–	1880
20	80	240, 600,730,1050	6,85	–	1880
10	90	650,900,1120	6,68	–	1880
5,0	95	720,1000,1045	6,59	–	1860
0,0	100	810, 1155	6,51	–	1850

The microhardness and density of alloys of the TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ system were studied depending on the composition (Table 1). As a result of measuring the microhardness of alloys, two different values were discovered. The microhardness of the δ-solid solution obtained based on the TlSe compound varies within the range (700-780) MPa. The microhardness of α-solid solutions based on the CuCr₂Te₄ compound varies within the range (1850-1880) MPa.

Conclusion

Synthesized alloy system TlSe-CuCr₂Te₄ was studied by methods of physicochemical analysis and Tx phase diagram was constructed. The phase diagram of the system is quasi-binary, eutectic type. The composition of the eutectic formed by the compounds TlSe and CuCr₂Te₄ is 15 mol % CuCr₂Te₄ and at a temperature of 240°C. In the system at room temperature, the content of TlSe based solid solutions reaches 3 mol % CuCr₂Te₄, and solid solutions based on CuCr₂Te₄ up to

- 12 mol % TlSe. The dependence of the density and microhardness of alloys of the TlSe - CuCr₂Te₄ system on composition has been studied.

References

1. Bakhyshev A.E., Agaeva M.F. and Darvish A.M. Electrical and Optical Properties of TlInSe₂ Single Crystals // Phys. Stat.Sol.,1979(b), 91, k31-k33.
2. Gasanly N.H., Goncharov A.P., Dzhavadov B.M., Melnik N.N., Tagirov V.I., Vinogradov E.A. Optical Phonons in TlInSe₂ Single Crystals // Phys. Stat. Sol, 1979 (b), 92, k139.
3. Zirke j., Domer C., Tausend A., Wobig D. Infrared Spectra of Amorphous Thallium Selenide Alloys // J.Non-Cryst.Sol.,1977, V.24, No2, P. 283-290.
4. Selahattin Ozdemir, Mahmut Bucurgat. Photoelectrical properties of TlGaSe₂ Single Crystals. Solid State Sciences. 2014. V.33, P. 26-30. DOI:10.1016/j.solidstatesciences.2014.04.006
5. Mimura K., Ishizu T. et.al. Peculiar Linear Dispersive Bands Observed in Angle-Resolved Photoemission Spectra of Tl-Based Ternary Chalcogenide TlGaTe₂. J. JAP, 2011. V.50. 05FC05-1-58.
6. Veliev J.A., Aliev I.I., Mamedova A.Z. Phase equilibrium in the As₂S₃-TlSe system. Journal inorganic chemistry. 2007. T.52. No. 2. pp. 312-315.
7. Zargarova M.I., Mamedov A.N., Azhdarova J.S., Akhmedova (Veliev) J.A., Abilov C.I. Directory: Inorganic substances synthesized and studied in Azerbaijan. Baku. Ed. Elm. 2004. 462 p.
8. Aliev I.I., Gamidova Sh.A., Suleymanova M.G., Kahramanov Sh.T., Akhmedova J.A. The nature of chemical interaction and glass formation in the As₂Se₃-TlS system. Scientific journal. Archivist. 2022, T: 7, No.: 9(63), P.18-22.
9. Rzaev R.M., Aliyev I.I., Gashimov Kh.M., Ahmedova C.A. Synthesis and investigation of physico-chemical properties alloys of the As₂S₃-Tl₂Te₃ system UNEC. Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences Vol. 2, No. 2, 2022, P. 45-50.
10. Aliev I.I., Ragimova V.M., Ahmedova C.A., Shakhbazov M.G., Gashimov Kh.M. Investigation of phase formation and glass formation in the As₂Se₃-TlTe system. Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science, 2022, № 88, P. 3-10.
11. Aliyev I.I., Rzaev R.M., Hashimov Kh.M., Ahmedova C.A., Naghiyev T.G. An investigation of structural, thermo-physical, and photoelectric properties of glassy As₂Se₃-Tl₂Te₃ alloys Modern Physics letters B, Online Ready <https://doi.org/10.1142/SO217984924502324> Cited by: 0 (Source:Crossref).
12. Takeshi Suzuyama, Junji Awaka, Hiroki Yamamoto, Shuji Ebisu, Masakazu Ito, Takashi Suzuki, Takao Nakama, Katsuma Yagasaki, Shoichi Nagata. Ferromagnetic-phase transition in the spinel-type CuCr₂Te₄. Journal of Solid State Chemistry. 2006, V.179, P. 140-144.
13. Nakatani I., Nose H., Masumoto K. Magnetic properties of CuCr₂Se₄ single crystals. J. Phys. Chem. Solids. 1978, V.39, № 7, P. 743-749.
14. Physico-chemical properties of semiconductor substances. Directory. Moscow. Ed. Science.1979, 339p.
15. Riedel E., Horvath E.Z. Roentgenographische Untersuchung der systeme CuCr₂(S_{1-x}Se_x)₄ und CuCr₂(Se_{1-x}Te_x)₄. Anorg. Allg. Chem. 1973, V.399, P.219-223.